

**WHAT IS THE EFFECT OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC CHANGES IN THE WORLD
ON THE ECONOMY AND WHAT IMPORTANT MEASURES NEED TO BE TAKEN?****Komilova Mukammal Shavkatovna****Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction****Head of the "Economics" department.****Islam Sobirovich Bakhtiyarov****A student of the 401st economic group**

Annotation: Today, our country has really undergone a drastic change in its economy and has become one of the liberalized countries. GDP per capita is increasing every year. The scope of foreign investments is expanding, privileges and opportunities are being created for entrepreneurs.

Keywords: forecast, global, conceptual, bureaucratic, currency, export volume, sector, fiscal, monetary credit, import, trend, international context.

Meanwhile, the US Federal Reserve System lowered the base interest rate by 0.5 percentage points on March 3 in order to maintain economic activity in a stable state. It is important that this decision is the first time since the crisis of 2008. A special group for the development of small and medium entrepreneurship has been formed under the Ministry of Finance of the USA. Also, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) reduced the forecast of world economic growth in 2020 by 0.5%. The IHRT, a global economy already on the brink due to trade wars and political tensions, is facing the challenges of today's supply chain disruptions, slack demand for resources, a downward trend in tourism and declining consumer confidence due to illness.

According to the IHRT report, under the worst scenario (downside scenario), i.e., the global spread of the epidemic, due to anti-epidemic measures and panic, it will seriously damage production and lead to an economic recession, and global economic growth will be up to 1.5%. is predicted to decrease. In turn, it is said that the impact of this situation can be very strong and lasting for countries. In general, it is natural that the consequences of these negative trends in the global economy will affect Uzbekistan as a part of the globalized economy. Although Uzbekistan is not as highly interconnected as developed countries, the serious changes taking place in them cannot fail to have an impact on the country's economy. In particular, China is the

largest trade partner of Uzbekistan, and the foreign trade turnover with China in 2019 was 7.6 billion. dollars (compared to total foreign trade turnover - 18.1%), export - 2.5 billion, import - 5.1 billion dollars. The decrease in the demand for energy resources in China will lead to a decrease in the volume of exports of Uzbekistan to China, including the export of natural gas.

Taking into account the fact that energy sources and oil products (i.e., natural gas) occupy the 3rd place (14.1%) in Uzbekistan's export structure, and 36.4% of the total export volume to China is accounted for by energy sources and oil products, it can be concluded that this situation will lead to a decrease in foreign currency income to Uzbekistan. Also, the reduction of raw materials and components coming from China, the increase in transport costs, interruptions in production supply are likely to cause serious damage to the industrial sector of Uzbekistan. The reason is that China's share in the total import volume of machinery and equipment necessary for Uzbekistan's industry is 30.9%, and China's share is the largest (24.0%) in the volume of imports of chemical products and articles made from them. These and other reasons create the need to take important short-term measures regarding this situation in Uzbekistan. For this, first of all, it is necessary to provide additional support to the fiscal and monetary policy and strengthen the structural reforms in the country. These measures will help stabilize economic growth, increase consumer and investor confidence, and reduce uncertainty. Secondly, it is advisable to take measures aimed at strengthening the financial situation of enterprises and organizations, including reducing tax rates for a certain period of time, providing "tax holidays", "tax credits" and creating the possibility of long-term refunds, introducing mechanisms for quick VAT refunds. Banks should be allowed to help enterprises facing cash flow problems, especially small and medium-sized enterprises. Measures should be taken to reduce the cost of energy sources for regions and industries that are likely to suffer. At the same time, on March 9, another serious situation occurred in the world oil market, and the price of oil recorded its lowest level since 2014.

This situation occurred when the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) and Russia failed to reach an agreement to reduce oil production (supply) following a drop in global oil demand. Following this situation, the prices of shares of leading Russian companies, including "Gazprom", "Lukoil", "Rosneft", "Sberbank", "X5 Retail Group", "Novatek", "Severstal" and others, fell sharply on the London stock exchange. Against the background of the decline in world oil prices, the Russian ruble began to fall - the dollar rose to 72 rubles, and the euro rose to 82 rubles. It may affect the decrease in the volume of foreign currency in Uzbekistan. Also, as a result of the slowdown of the Russian economy, it may lead to

a reduction of the 3.4 billion dollars (5.9 percent compared to GDP) benefits that Uzbek migrants bring to our country. Taking into account that income from transfers makes up 25.3% of the total income of the population, this situation may affect the standard of living of the population in Uzbekistan to a certain extent. For this, it is appropriate to take measures to stimulate economic activity and support employment. In particular, it is necessary to expand the financing of small businesses, to extend the preferential period of loans. It is necessary to declare a moratorium on all permitting and bureaucratic procedures for a certain period of time, quickly solve the obstacles and problems arising in business activities, take drastic measures to ensure employment, and encourage the creation of short-term jobs.

These measures serve to reduce the impact of external global economic consequences on Uzbekistan and balance the economic situation. At this point, it should be noted that the central banks of many countries have lowered the key interest rates, not in the financial sector, but in the real sector of the economy, aimed at increasing investment attractiveness. If we proceed from the experience of 2008, it was observed that the capital flow moved from developed countries to developing countries (China). For this reason, taking into account the possibility of Uzbekistan taking advantage of the current situation, it is important to focus on creating a favorable investment environment and increase investment attractiveness. Today, our country has become one of the liberalized countries with a sharp change in its economy. GDP per capita is increasing every year. The scope of foreign investments is expanding, privileges and opportunities are being created for entrepreneurs. In the past six years, large-scale work has been carried out to improve the living standards of all strata of the population through the rapid development of the economy in our country. Systematic measures were taken to ensure liberalization, openness and transparency in various aspects of socio-economic life. The work in this regard will continue intensively. In particular, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev also paid attention to this issue at the recently held joint session of the parliamentary chambers and emphasized the need not to be limited by the achieved achievements and to conquer new goals in the future. In particular, by 2030, the gross domestic product doubling the volume of production to 160 billion dollars, increasing the gross domestic product per capita from the current 2,200 dollars to 4,000 dollars will be one of our main strategic goals. First of all, based on advanced technologies Necessary measures will be taken to develop the industry and thereby increase labor productivity by 2 times.

At the same time, until 2030, every opportunity will be used to increase the production of copper, which is necessary for a high-income product, by 3.5 times, gold by 1.5 times, silver by

3 times, and uranium by 3 times. Real competition will appear in the automotive industry. Launching the projects of 4 prestigious foreign companies and increasing the production volume to 1 million units per year is one of our main priorities. Necessary measures will be taken to ensure the production of 300,000 electric cars per year. All conditions will be created so that the value added in the industry will increase from 20 billion dollars to 45 billion dollars. The transition to the rapidly developing "Green economy" in the whole world, the use of renewable energy, which is its basis, will be expanded. By 2030, it is important to increase the volume of renewable energy sources to 25 thousand megawatts, and their share from the current 14% to 40%. Starting from 2024, the market of "green certificates" will be created in the industry. necessary conditions for the production of "green energy" are created. It is planned to build 10,000 kilometers of highway and 110,000 kilometers of regional power grids, which will be implemented on the basis of specific programs. Uzbekistan's economy will grow by 5.5% in 2023. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) report explained whether Uzbekistan can slow down price growth. The information was published in the next report on the development prospects of the world economy. Despite the complex geopolitical situation in the region and the world, the economy will continue to recover. However, the economic outlook remains volatile amid the Russia-Ukraine conflict, economic slowdown, and inflationary pressures. The growth of remittances, as well as the growth of capital and migrant flows, will begin to change from 2023. S&P positively assesses the program of economic reforms to increase the efficiency of state-owned enterprises and implement privatization in Uzbekistan.

This will have a positive effect on the economy dominated by the public sector. Due to geopolitical tensions in the region and the unstable outlook of the global economy, large-scale privatization will take time. Analysts expect the economic environment to support credit growth of 25-30 percent by 2024, compared to moderate growth in 2022. Despite some gains, dollarization is likely to remain high for the next two years. In 2022, the gross domestic product per capita increased by 9.3% and amounted to 2146.7 dollars. However, due to the significant size of the underground economy, the real income of the population may be higher than the official income. Net government debt is projected to reach 23 percent of GDP by 2025, a low level by international standards. The current account deficit will average 6 percent of GDP over the next three years, but will be financed by foreign direct investment and debt inflows. 5-6 years is a short time for major reforms, but in this short period of time, modern mechanisms were introduced in the economic sphere in terms of tax policy, fundamental revision of the budget system, and regulation of the monetary and credit system. One of the most important steps in

eliminating systemic problems and structural imbalances in the economy was the liberalization of the foreign exchange market. New Tax and Budget Codes have been adopted in order to conduct a tax-budget policy consistent with economic reforms and to allocate budget funds effectively, and this state budget is being adopted as a law. At the legislative level, legal norms that provide sufficiently flexible conditions for managing risks and external influences are being incorporated into our national legislation, and fiscal regulations are being improved. Over the past six years, 14 new laws have been adopted on the legal basis of coordination of tax, budget, monetary policy and other economic processes. 9 laws were declared invalid. Also, 273 amendments and additions were made to 50 current laws.

All this serves to improve the legal basis for the implementation of comprehensive economic reforms. In general, in June 2023, it was observed that the inflation rate of Uzbekistan's economy in general decreased, and the exchange rate remained relatively stable. Also, the growth of foreign trade in May significantly accelerated compared to the corresponding period of the previous year. In January-May of this year, the foreign trade turnover of Uzbekistan amounted to 25.8 billion dollars and increased by 25.4% compared to the same period last year. Exports amounted to 10.5 billion dollars, while imports amounted to 15.3 billion dollars. Growth of export and import was 24.1 percent and 26.4 percent, respectively. The negative balance of foreign trade amounted to 4.8 billion dollars. For comparison, in the corresponding period of 2022, the foreign trade deficit amounted to 3.6 billion dollars. Goods and services worth 2.8 billion dollars were exported in May, which increased by 2.3 times compared to the same period last year. In this case, the main factor influencing the growth of exports was the export of gold. In particular, gold worth 1.3 billion dollars was exported in May. In May, exports without gold also increased in relatively high figures. In particular, in April, the monthly gold-free export decreased by 5%, while in May, the growth rate of gold-free export was 22%.

The document was published in UzA. In accordance with the Presidential Decree No. PF-158 dated 11.09.2023 "On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030", it is planned to implement measures in all spheres of social and economic life of the country in the year of human attention and quality education. In conclusion, we can say that as a result of the deepening of economic reforms, we will achieve positive results in the production of industrial products, improvement of the financial situation, payments to the state budget and extra-budgetary funds, and similar tasks. The guarantee of freedom of entrepreneurship in the Constitution, the clear definition of the obligations of the state in creating a healthy competitive environment, the protection of property and other rights of the individual in accordance with the law, increase the confidence of our

people in the state policy and reforms aimed at realizing the principle of "Social State". That is, in the development of Uzbekistan, the conceptual aspects of the full implementation of the priority principle "For the dignity of man" were reflected in our Constitution. Now it is our turn to incorporate all the legal criteria and principles defined in our General Encyclopaedia in this regard into our lives. Improving the legal foundations of economic reforms, formalizing the legal foundations that ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of reforms has an important place in law-making. In this regard, the Legislative Chamber and its respective responsible committees are defining specific plans for themselves.

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